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METHODS OF ORGANIZING CONTINUOUS REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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ABSTRACT

Purpose to develop available physical exercises that increase the effectiveness of therapy in patients with cerebral palsy. Objects and methods. 54 patients with cerebral palsy with different forms were examined and rehabilitated. In the main group, classes at home were added to complex treatment. The effectiveness of therapy by category: communication, movement, self-service, play activity, was more in the group where therapeutic exercise was used. The conclusion. The need for further development of methods for the rehabilitation of children with disabilities is shown.

Keywords: Children's cerebral palsy, exercise therapy, massage, exercise, rehabilitation event.

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МЕТОДЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ НЕПРЕРЫВНОЙ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ БОЛЬНЫХ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассмотрены роль физической культуры в домашних условиях вместе с матерями. Мы исследовали детей которые лечатся в первой клинике Самаркандской Медицинской

Институте 2 раза в год. Для детей с детским церебральным параличом лечится 2 раза в год по 10 дней дает очень мало эффект. По этому мы решили заниматься с ними каждый день в течение нескольких месяцев и даже годами. Для этого научили мам заниматься с детьми. Целью работы является разработка доступных физических упражнений, которые повышают эффективность терапии у больных ДЦП.

Произведено обследование и реабилитация 54 больных ДЦП с разными формами. В основной группе к комплексному лечению добавлены занятия в домашних условиях. Результативность терапии по категориям: общение, передвижение, самообслуживание, игровая деятельность – была больше в группе, где применялись лечебная физкультура в домашних условиях. Заключение. Показана необходимость дальнейшей разработки методов реабилитации детей – инвалидов

Ключевые слова: детский церебральный паралич, лечебная физкультура, массаж, упражнение, реабилитационные мероприятия.

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MIYA FALAJLI BOLALARDA UZLUKSIZ REABILITATSIYANI TASHKIL ETISH USULLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada onalar bilan uyda jismoniy tarbiyaning roli ko'rib chiqiladi. Yiliga 2 marta Samarqand tibbiyot institutining birinchi poliklinikasida davolanayotgan bolalarni o'rgandik. Miya falajli bolalar uchun yiliga 2 marta 10 kun davomida davolash juda kam samara beradi. Shuning uchun biz buni har kuni bir necha oy va hatto yillar davomida qilishga qaror qildik. Buning uchun ular onalarga farzandlari bilan ishlashni o'rgatishgan. Miya falajli bemorlarda terapiya samaradorligini oshiradigan qulay jismoniy mashqlarni ishlab chiqish maqsadi qo'yildi Turli shakldagi miya falajiga chalingan 54 nafar bemorni tekshirish va rehabilitatsiya qilish ishlari olib borildi. Asosiy guruhda kompleks davolashga uy mashqlari qo'shildi. Kategoriyalar bo'yicha terapiya samaradorligi aloqa, harakat, o'z-o'zini parvarish qilish, o'yin faoliyati uyda qo'llanilgan guruhda ko'proq edi.

Nogiron bolalarni rehabilitatsiya qilish usullarini yanada rivojlantirish zarurligi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: miya yarim falaji, fizioterapiya, massaj, jismoniy mashqlar, reabilitatsion tadbirlar.

Kirish: Nogironlikning barcha shakllariga qarshi kurash davlat ahamiyatiga molik masaladir. Nogironlikning eng og'ir shakllaridan biri bu intrauterin va tug'ilish bilan bog'liq miya shikastlanishi bilan bog'liq nogironlikdir. Ushbu toifadagi nogiron bolalar orasida miya falajiga chalingan nogironlar alohida ajralib turadi. Miya falaji tufayli nogironlikning og'irligi, vosita buzilishlari bilan bir qatorda, qoida tariqasida, og'ir ruhiy va nutq buzilishlari ham mavjudligi bilan bog'liq. Miya falaji bilan og'rigan bemorlarning taxminan 20 foizi o'zlariga g'amxo'rlik qila olmaydi va ularni o'rganish mumkin emas. Shunday qilib, miya yarim falajining oldini olish va rehabilitatsiya terapiyasi masalasi tibbiy muammo doirasidan oshib boradi va tobora ijtimoiy ma'no kasb etadi: nafaqat individual biologik, balki mehnat, ijtimoiy foydali faoliyatni ta'minlaydigan funktsiyalar ham azoblanadi.

Hozirgi vaqtda miya yarim palsi bilan og'rigan bolalarni davolash ixtisoslashtirilgan bolalar nevrologiya bo'limlarida, bolalar psixonevrologiya klinikalarida va ixtisoslashtirilgan bolalar bog'chalarida jamlangan. Maktab-internatlar va bolalar uylari, ixtisoslashtirilgan bolalar sanatoriylari. Miya falajiga qarshi ishimizning maqsadi - harakatlarni ixtiyoriy ravishda inhibe qilish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish, mushaklarning gipertonikligini kamaytirish, harakatlarni muvofiqlashtirishni yaxshilash, bo'g'inlardagi harakatlarning amplitudasini oshirish, shuningdek,

bolalarga uy-ro'zg'or ko'nikmalarini o'rgatish. Dastur ibtidoiy reflekslarni kamaytirish, vosita kuchini oshirish, tana muvozanatini saqlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish va ritmik harakatlarni amalga oshirishga qaratilgan.

Tadqiqot usullari: Tadqiqotimizda 1 yoshdan 6 yoshgacha bo'lgan 54 nafar bola ishtirok etdi. Biz ularni 2 guruhga ajratdik. Ikkala guruh ham klinikada standart davolanishni oldi. Biz 33 nafar bolani nazorat guruhiga oldik va uyda terapevtik mashqlarni davom ettirdik. Biz miya yarim palsi uchun mashqlar terapiyasini quyidagi metodologiyadan foydalangan holda amalga oshirdik: mashg'ulotlarning muntazamligi, tizimliliigi va uzluksizligi, kasallikning bosqichi va og'irligini, shuningdek, bolaning yoshi va aqliy rivojlanishini hisobga olgan holda individual yondashuv. Biz onalarga nutq terapiyasi massajini o'rgatganmiz. U yuz va artikulyar mushaklarning massajidan iborat bo'lib, mushaklarning ohangini normallashtirishga yordam beradi va vosita hissiyotlarini rag'batlantiradi. Ushbu massaj texnikasi quyidagicha:

A) Silliqlash. Peshonani o'rtadan chakkagacha, so'ngra qoshlardan bosh terisigacha, quloq bo'laklaridan yonoq bo'ylab burun qanotlarigacha, yuqori lab bo'ylab, pastki lab bo'ylab silliqdash.

B) Tilning bo'shashishi. Biz submandibulyar chuqurchadagi nuqtani massaj qilamiz va jag'ning burchaklarida tebranish harakatlarini qilamiz.

B) Og'iz bo'shlig'i mushaklarining bo'shashishi. Yumshoq harakatlardan foydalanib, peshona, yonoq, bo'yin, lablar va tilning mushaklarini massaj qiling. Biz nazolabial burmalarni silaymiz.

D) Bo'yin muskullarining bo'shashishi. Biz bo'yinni massaj qilamiz va passiv bosh burilishlarini qilamiz.

D) Tilning giperkineziga akupressura. Biz lab maydonini, pastki jag' maydonini va popliteal sohadagi nuqtalarni massaj qilamiz.

Bundan tashqari, biz onalarga etakchi va antagonistik mushak guruhlarini kuchaytirish uchun o'zaro ta'sir qilish mashqlarini, organlar faoliyati samaradorligini saqlab qolish uchun chidamlilik mashqlarini, spazmlar, taranglik va kramplarni bartaraf etish uchun bo'shashish mashqlarini, yurish mashqlarini va muvozanat va vosita kuchini yaxshilash uchun toqqa chiqish mashqlarini o'rgatdi. .

Uch yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarga vestibulyar apparatlarning faoliyatini normallashtirishga yordam beradigan mashqlar berildi. Bunday mashqlar quyidagi harakatlarni o'z ichiga oladi: orqa va oshqozon ustida yotish, boshingizni ko'tarish, tanangizni egish. Shuningdek, biz yurish mashqlarini ham kiritdik, unda siz boshingizni burishingiz, qo'llaringizni yuqoriga ko'tarishingiz, oldinga siljishingiz va ko'zingizni yumishingiz kerak. Ajoyib ta'sirga erishish uchun biz mashqlar terapiyasini massaj bilan birlashtirdik.

Klassik massaj kurslarda, 8-10 seansda va 5 kunlik tanaffusda o'tkazildi. Bu mushaklarning spazmlarini kamaytirish va bo'shashgan mushaklarni kuchaytirish uchun amalga oshirildi. Buning uchun turli xil usullar qo'llanilgan: taroqsimon, forseps shaklidagi va spazm holatida konsentrik silash, mushaklarning atoniyasida yo'gurma va urish. Bu massaj bolaning tutqanoqlari yo'qolganda boshlangan. Acupressure gevşeme massaji mashqlar terapiyasi va boshqa massaj turlariga qo'shimcha sifatida ishlatilgan. Buning uchun hech qanday kontrendikatsiya yo'q, buni har kuni faqat vaqti-vaqti bilan tanaffuslar bilan qilishingiz mumkin. Massaj texnikasi kasal bolaning ota-onasiga o'rgatilgan, shuning uchun ular har kuni oylar davomida mashq qilishgan. Reabilitatsiya tadbirlari doimiy ravishda amalga oshirilib, maksimal samara beradigan narsaga e'tibor qaratildi. Faqat bu holatda siz barqaror natijalarga ishonishingiz mumkin. Ma'lumki, miya yarim palsi kasalligini davolash murakkab, uzoq muddatli bo'lib, harakatga, buzilgan harakatlarni tiklashga, buzilgan funktsiyalarni tiklashga qaratilgan bo'lib, ota-onalarning tinimsiz mehnati bilan erishiladi. Bularning barchasini ota-onalarga tushuntirib, kasal bolalar bilan birga ishladi. Kundalik fizioterapiya va massaj chaqaloqlarning normal rivojlanishiga yordam berdi. Fizioterapiya mashg'ulotlarining boshlanishi ijobiy o'zgarishlarga olib keldi: bolaning hissiy holati yaxshilandi, mushaklarning kontrakturasi kamaydi. Miya falajining dastlabki bosqichida pozitsion davolash bo'shashtiruvchi massaj va gevşeme mashqlaridan so'ng amalga oshirildi. Tanaga fiziologik jihatdan to'g'ri pozitsiyani berish uchun qumli maxsus rolik va yumshoq ichki qoplamali shinalar ishlatilgan. Kattaroq yoshda mushaklarni biriktirish nuqtalarining maksimal yaqinlashuvi bilan pozitsiya ishlatilgan. Poza giperkinezni inhiye qilish va servikal-tonik assimetrik refleksning ta'sirini kamaytirish imkonini

berdi. Parallel ravishda amalga oshiriladigan akupressura yordamida siz qo'lning faol fleksiyasini va kengayishini rag'batlantirishingiz mumkin.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Standart davolanishdan so'ng, uyda fizika terapiyasi bilan shug'ullanadigan bolalar asta-sekin intensivlikdagi mashqlarni bajarish orqali mushaklar kuchini rivojlantirishga muvaffaq bo'lishdi. Miya falajiga qarshi terapevtik jismoniy tarbiya bolani o'z tanasidan foydalanishga va uning individual xususiyatlariga qarab mushaklarga vosita signallarini muvofiqlashtirishga o'rgatdi, chunki boshqa barcha odamlar foydalanadigan tug'ma vosita reflekslari muvaffaqiyatsizlikka uchradi. Doimiy mashg'ulotlar mushaklarning noto'g'ri ohangiga qarshi kurashishga imkon berdi, bu ayniqsa pareziya holatida samarali ishladi. Miya falajli bolalarda jismoniy mashqlar terapiyasidan so'ng asab tizimi qisman tiklandi, bu bolada hali ham juda moslashuvchan va ma'lum darajada tashqi ta'sir ostida o'zgarishi, tiklanishi va hatto qayta tiklanishi mumkin. Jismoniy terapiya majmuasi qanchalik erta boshlansa va mashg'ulotlar qanchalik yaxshi, mas'uliyatli va qizg'in bo'lsa, bola o'zining jismoniy nogironligining o'rnini to'ldirishga qodir bo'lib, nafaqat tanasidan foydalanishni yoki o'ziga g'amxo'rlik qilishni, balki tezda o'rganadi. u yoki bu darajada faol hayot kechira oldi. avval o'smirlik, keyin esa yigitlik hayoti. Ota-onalarning borligi bolalarning ma'naviyatini oshirdi, ularni yanada chidamli qildi, ko'proq harakat qildi yoki ayniqsa mashaqqatli mashqlar paytida ularni taskinladi. Suzish nafaqat hovuzda, balki oddiy hammomda ham bajarilishi mumkin bo'lgan universal usul edi. Jismoniy terapiya miya yarim palsi bo'lgan bolalar uchun juda foydali. Ular bolaning ahvolini kamida ikki baravar oshirishga imkon berdi, shuningdek, uni dunyoda omon qolish va hatto ishlashga qodir qildi. Darslar qanchalik erta boshlangan bo'lsa, ular shunchalik samarali bo'ldi, ammo shunga qaramay, ularni boshlash hech qachon kech emas. O'rganish va ijtimoiy moslashish imkoniyati ko'p jihatdan kompensatsiyaning to'liqligi va aqliy zaiflik darajasiga bog'liq. Spastik diplegiya bilan og'rigan bolalar o'zlariga g'amxo'rlik qilishni o'rganishlari va yozish uchun bir qator mehnat ko'nikmalarini egallashlari mumkin edi. Skiperkinetik shakli bo'lgan bolalar o'rganish va ijtimoiy moslashish uchun qulay prognozga ega edi. Atonik-astatik miya yarim palsi bo'lgan bolalar uzoq vaqt davomida davolanishi kerak. Kursimizdan so'ng ular ham yaxshi o'zgarishlarni ko'rsatishdi. Sezgilarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan rejalashtirilgan mashqlar to'plamidan foydalanib, biz asab tizimida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolaning motor sohasi holatini yaxshilashimiz mumkin. Birinchi guruhda bu sanab o'tilgan barcha natijalar oshkor etilmagan. Har bir miya yarim palsi foriyasi uchun vosita funktsiyalari har xil bo'lganligi sababli, spastik dplegiya uchun biz doimiy harakatni talab qiladigan nisbatan oson o'rganiladigan mashqlarni buyurdik. Va astatik shakl bilan qisqa muddatli mashqlar, bu mashqlar orasida tez-tez dam olishga imkon beradi. Atonik shakl boshqa bir qator muammolarni keltirib chiqardi. Ayniqsa, falajning ushbu shakli bo'lgan bolalar muvozanat mashqlari paytida azoblanadi. Erishtilgan muvaffaqiyatlarni mustahkamlash uchun mashg'ulotlarning xilma-xilligi va yangiligi yangilandi va takrorlandi. Bir tomondan, shikastlangan miyani tiklashga imkon beradigan davolash yo'q. Biroq, agar siz ilmiy asoslangan dastur bo'yicha ishlasangiz, u holda buzilmagan holatda bo'lgan asab tizimi barcha funktsiyalarini bajarishi mumkin. Jismoniy tarbiya dasturlari miya yarim palsi bilan kasallangan bolalarni har tomonlama rehabilitatsiya qilishda etakchi o'rin tutadi. Biz miya yarim palsi bilan kasallangan har bir bemorning motor muhitining xususiyatlarini sinchkovlik bilan tahlil qildik va vosita funktsiyalarini rag'batlantirishga imkon beradigan dastur yaratdik. Mashqlar to'plamini tuzishda biz miya yarim palsi bilan og'rigan bemorlarga (spastik diplegiya yoki atonik shaklda) e'tibor qaratdik, chunki ular bajaradigan mashqlar mushaklarning majburiy harakatlariga qaraganda ko'proq faollikni talab qiladi.

Xulosa: Shunday qilib, miya yarim palsi - davolab bo'lmaydigan kasallik, ammo uyda jismoniy terapiya uning oqibatlari va sindromlarini engillashtirishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga, dori-darmonlarni qo'llash bolaning ahvolini yanada yaxshilaydi. Ona bilan bu mashqlarning barchasi bemorning tashqi sharoitlarga moslashishida katta rol o'ynaydi. Uy sharoitida biz taklif qilayotgan fizioterapiya mashqlari eng samarali, bajarilishi oson va oldingi guruhga nisbatan juda yaxshi natijalar berdi. Uyda o'qigan bolalar, hech bo'lmaganda, o'zlariga g'amxo'rlik qilishni o'rgandilar. Gipertoniklikda ohang pasaygan, aksincha, gipotoniklik kuchaygan. Bu shuni anglatadiki, nafaqat shifoxona va sanatoriylarda, balki uyda ham, agar ota-onalar miya yarim palsi bilan kasallangan bolalar bilan shug'ullansa, unda natijalar ancha yuqori bo'ladi.

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